

1 **Metabolic derangement in active CD: II.**

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- 6 ● OLAH activation
- 7 ● GLUL activation
- 8 ● ARG2 change
- 9 ○ Phenotype is similar to that found in the blood of children with asthma (i.e., the metabolite phenotype appears to be a biologically significant component of immune disease in humans)

10 Citations

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13 2. Palanki, R., Yamagata, H. and Mitchell, M.J., 2024. OLAH connects fatty acid metabolism to the severity of respiratory viral disease. *Cell*, 187(17), pp.4549-4551.

14 3. Zhang, Y., Higgins, C.B., Fortune, H.M., Chen, P., Stothard, A.I., Mayer, A.L., Swarts, B.M. and DeBosch, B.J., 2019. Hepatic arginase 2 (Arg2) is sufficient to convey the therapeutic metabolic effects of fasting. *Nature communications*, 10(1), p.1587.